

QUINOLINE COMPLEXES OF ZINC AND CADMIUM SULPHATES AND THEIR HEATS OF FORMATION

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Quinoline complexes of zinc sulphate and cadmium sulphate have been prepared. They have the formulae $[\text{Zn} \cdot 2\text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{N}] \text{SO}_4 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $[\text{Cd} \cdot 2\text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{N} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}] \text{SO}_4 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ respectively. The heats of formation of these compounds have been determined calorimetrically by the method of solution. The heats of formation of the zinc and cadmium compounds are 15,704 and 17,206 calories/G. F. W respectively. It appears that the introduction of water molecules inside the complex increases its stability.

A large number of complexes of quinoline with various inorganic salts is known, but no attempt has yet been made to make a systematic study of these complexes. All the earlier works are concerned mainly with the preparation and analysis of the complex formed, and except the solubility, decomposition temperature and a few crystallographic data, little regarding the physical properties of these complexes is recorded in literature. Heat data, which are of importance in determining their stability, in obtaining a comparative picture of the complexes of different organic heterocyclic bases with inorganic salt, and in arriving at any kind of generalisation, are not available. In the present investigation the quinoline complexes of the sulphates of zinc and cadmium have been prepared and their heats of formation determined directly by calorimetric measurements. The sulphates of zinc and cadmium have been chosen because no quinoline complexes of these salts are known.

The quinoline complexes of zinc and cadmium were first prepared by Schiff (*Compt. rend.*, 1863, 57, 838; *Annalen*, 1864, 131, 112). He obtained the quinoline complexes of the chlorides and iodides of zinc and cadmium and established their compositions as $\text{ZnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{Q}$, $\text{ZnI}_2 \cdot 2\text{Q}$, $\text{CdCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{Q}$ and $\text{CdI}_2 \cdot 2\text{Q}$, by analysis. Borsbach (*Ber.*, 1890, 23, 43) also obtained the same compounds and found that they were only slightly soluble in water and alcohol. He also prepared the complexes, $\text{CdCl}_2 \cdot \text{Q}$ and $\text{CdBr}_2 \cdot \text{Q}$ and also complexes of the type $\text{CdCl}_2 \cdot \text{Q} \cdot \text{HCl} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$. Reitzenstein (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1898, 18, 295) confirmed the formation of the complex $\text{CdBr}_2 \cdot 2\text{Q}$. Hugo (*Chem. Zentr.*, 1905, II, 139) has given the crystallographic data of zinc and cadmium quinoline complexes of the type $\text{Zn}(\text{NCS})_2 \cdot 2\text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{N} \cdot \text{NCS}$, $\text{ZnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{N} \cdot \text{Cl}$, $\text{ZnBr}_2 \cdot 2\text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{N} \cdot \text{Br}$, $\text{ZnI}_2 \cdot 2\text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{N} \cdot \text{I}$ and $\text{CdBr}_2 \cdot 2\text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{N} \cdot \text{Br}$. No quinoline complex of either zinc sulphate or cadmium sulphate was known. More recently, Chang and Yü (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1939, 243, 14) studied the complexes of quinoline with some bivalent heavy metals. They prepared the compounds, $2\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{N}$, $2\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot \text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{N}$, $2\text{CoSO}_4 \cdot \text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{N}$ and $2\text{HgSO}_4 \cdot \text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{N}$. As a result of their investigation they came to the conclusion that the presence of a multivalent anion decreases the tendency of the bivalent metals to form complexes with quinoline. The present work, however, does not support their observation.

EXPERIMENTAL

Freshly distilled quinoline (20 c.c.) was taken in a tall beaker and a saturated solution of zinc sulphate or cadmium sulphate was added to it dropwise from a burette

until no further crystals separated. The liquid was kept vigorously agitated by means of an electrically operated stirrer. The stirring was continued for several hours even after the addition of the sulphate solution had been completed. The crystals were collected on a Buchner funnel, washed with a little acetone, dried between folds of filter paper and preserved.

The analysis of the compounds thus obtained was carried out as follows: Quinoline was determined by weighing out a small quantity of the substance into an Erlenmeyer's flask, treating with an excess of *N*/10-hydrochloric acid and titrating back the excess of acid with standard NaOH solution, using methyl orange as an indicator. Zinc was estimated by precipitating as zinc ammonium phosphate and weighing as zinc pyrophosphate. Cadmium was determined as the sulphide and the sulphate ion was estimated in the usual way by precipitating with barium chloride. The results of analysis are set down in Table I.

TABLE I

Complex.	Found.	Calc.
$ZnSO_4 \cdot 2Q \cdot 6H_2O$	Zn, 11.5, 11.4, 11.2%	11.6%
	Q, 46.0, 45.9, 45.6	45.8
	SO ₄ , 17.6, 17.4, 17.2	17.4
	H ₂ O, —	25.2
$CdSO_4 \cdot 2Q \cdot 6H_2O$	Cd, 20.0, 19.8, 19.4%	19.6
	Q, 45.2, 44.8, 44.2	44.9
	SO ₄ , 17.1, 16.8, 16.6	16.7
	H ₂ O, —	18.8

Both the compounds are colorless and crystalline. They are not hygroscopic, and both are decomposed by water, the zinc complex being more so. They are readily soluble in mineral acids, but are insoluble in acetone, alcohol and chloroform. When the hydrated compounds were kept over concentrated sulphuric acid in a vacuum desiccator at 30°, it was found that the zinc compound lost all the water in one week and the anhydrous complex, $ZnSO_4 \cdot 2C_9H_7N$, was left. Under the same conditions the cadmium compound, however, lost only 4 molecules of water and the remaining two molecules of water were retained permanently. There was no loss even after the crystals were left in the desiccator for over a month.

The heats of formation of the complexes were determined by solution methods. The heat of solution of the complex in 2*N*-sulphuric acid was first determined and then the heat of solution of quinoline in sulphuric acid of the same strength was measured similarly. Knowing the heat of solution of pure zinc sulphate or cadmium sulphate (cf. International Critical Tables), it is possible to calculate the heats of formation of the complexes from the results obtained. The method of calorimetry was similar to that used by Patrick and Grimm (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, **43**, 2144). The calorimeter

consisted of a silvered Dewar flask of 100 c. c. capacity. It was fitted with a rubber cover in which were mounted a 5° Beckmann thermometer, a Nichrome-wire heater, and a copper stirrup which served as a stirrer as well as a holder for the glass bulbs in which a weighed quantity of the complex or quinoline had been sealed. The glass bulbs were broken beneath the surface of the liquid by means of a rod. The vacuum flask contained a charge of only 25 c. c. of 2*N*-sulphuric acid and it was found that intermittent manual stirring was sufficient to keep the temperature equalised. Repeated calibration using a measured heat input through the Nichrome coil showed that the reproducibility of the measurements was quite good. To prevent the action of acid, etc., the Nichrome wire was wound round a thin strip of mica and immersed in oil contained in a thin-walled glass tube, similar to the one used by Tucker (*Trans. Roy. Soc.*, 1915, 218, 319) in his heat of dilution experiments. The results of measurements are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

Substance.	Weight.	Temp rise (corr. °C).	Thermal capacity of calorimeter.	Heat of solution. G.F.W.	Mean.
ZnSO ₄ · 2C ₉ H ₇ N · 8H ₂ O	(1) 1.4882 g.	0.702°	58.2	15,440	Q ₁ 15,286
	(2) 1.5500	0.704°	58.4	14,940	
	(3) 1.5723	0.742°	58.3	15,480	
Quinoline	(1) 1.3333	1.112°	58.2	6,252	Q ₂ 6,286
	(2) 0.9430	0.800°	58.0	6,348	
	(3) 0.6149	0.512°	58.1	6,241	
CdSO ₄ · 2C ₉ H ₇ N · 6H ₂ O	(1) 1.0984	0.202°	58.1	6,138	Q ₁ 6,094
	(2) 1.2238	0.225°	58.2	6,116	
	(3) 1.3101	0.242°	58.0	6,030	
ZnSO ₄				18,430	Q ₂ International Critical Table
CdSO ₄				10,740	

If the heat of solution of complex is Q_1 and those of quinoline and ZnSO₄ or CdSO₄ are Q_2 and Q_3 respectively, then the heat of formation of the complex, according to Hess' law, is $Q_3 + 2Q_2 - Q_1$. Heats formation of the two complexes, ZnSO₄ · 2C₉H₇N · 8H₂O and CdSO₄ · 2C₉H₇N · 6H₂O work out to 15,704 calories/G. F. W and 17,206 calories/G. F. W. respectively. The effect of a small amount of water present in the crystals of the complexes being extremely small is neglected in the calculations.

DISCUSSION

The facts that the whole of the water in the zinc complex is readily removable and the sulphate ion is capable of complete ionisation indicate that the formula of the

zinc compound is $[Zn.2C_9H_7N]SO_4.8H_2O$. In the case of the cadmium compound, however, only 4 molecules of water can be removed by dehydration, but 2 molecules of water are permanently retained, indicating that these 2 molecules of water form part of the complex itself. Hence the formula of this compound seems to be $[Cd.2C_9H_7N.2H_2O]SO_4.4H_2O$

It has been found that heat of formation of $[Zn.2C_9H_7N]SO_4.8H_2O$ is 15,602 calories/G.F.W. and that $[Cd.2C_9H_7N.2H_2O]SO_4.4H_2O$ is 17,198 calories/G. F. W. showing that the cadmium compound is more stable than the zinc compound. It is probable that the introduction of two H_2O molecules in the complex increases the stability of the compound. The heats of formation are comparable in magnitude with those of similar complexes of pyridine.

The work of Schiff, Borsbach, and Reitzenstein (*loc. cit.*) shows that the chlorides, bromides and iodides of zinc and cadmium form, with quinoline, complexes almost identical in composition with the sulphates of these metals. The stability of the quinoline complexes of zinc and cadmium salts appears to be of the same order whether the anions are univalent or bivalent. The present work therefore does not support the conclusion of Chang and Yü (*loc. cit.*) that the presence of a multivalent anion decreases the tendency of the bivalent metals to form complexes with quinoline.

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